

PSYCHOLOGICAL STATUS BETWEEN THE ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL STUDIES STUDENTS OF KALYANI UNIVERSITY

Dr.Laden Lepcha¹, Sujit Mondal², Chitra Bhar³

¹Assistant Professor, ^{2,3}Research Scholar
Department of Physical Education
University of Kalyani, WB, 741235, India.

Abstract: Objective: The main purpose of the study is to observe the differences of Stress Level between the adult of Engineering and Social Studies Students of University of Kalyani.

Subjects: Sixty (N=60) adult students were randomly selected as subject for the present study from University of Kalyani, Nadia District of West Bengal, India. The age ranges from 19 to 25 years.

Group division: All the Subjects were divided into two groups: (i) Engineering Students, University of Kalyani, Nadia, W.B (N=30) (ii) Social Studies Students, University of Kalyani, Nadia, W.B (N=30).

Methods: The Psychological status Stress of adult university students were measured through Questionnaire of A.K.Srivastava (2001).

Statistical analysis: to find out the significance differences in psychological status between the groups, Analysis of 't' test was conducted. The significance of means were tested at $p < 0.05$ level.

Result: It was observed that 't' test was significant at 0.05 levels. It is statistically significant differences between the groups in Behavioral Approach, Cognitive Behavioral Approach, Behavioral Avoidance and Cognitive Avoidance.

Keywords: Behavioral Approach, Cognitive Approach, Cognitive Behavioral Approach, Behavioral Avoidance and Cognitive Avoidance, Adult University Students.

Introduction:

Today's technologically developed world and modern lifestyle and food habits has welcome most unwanted challenges and has lost the harmony in mind body relationship. It has caused several physiological and psychological stress based diseases like anxiety, hypertension, coronary disease, cancer etc. Abounded of clinical studies has confirmed that physical exercise practice helps to promote a balanced development of physical, mental and spiritual wellbeing (Lepcha, 2016 & 2023).

Stress has become a common phenomenon in our daily lives, which certainly has positive as well as negative influence on human behavior. Gradually it leads them toward utter frustration and stress which in later years causes physiological as well as psychological problem (Schuler, 1980).

Engineering students is avowed as a stressful environment that creates a negative effect on the academic performance as well as physical health and psychological wellbeing. Various Studies on psychological problems such as stress, depression and anxiety among engineering students have found that these disorders are under diagnosed and under treated. While high levels of stress are common amongst university students, particularly engineering students (Munaf, 2017).

Stress tends to occur together. Stress is also associate with feeling of loneliness, peer competition, loss of social time, Behavioral and Cognitive Approach quality in this backdrop the present study has been undertaken to understand the level of stress between the engineering and social studies students of kalyani university.

2.Method

Total sixty (60), adult university students of age between 19-25 years were randomly selected from University of Kalyani, Nadia district in West Bengal, India. All the Subjects were divided into two groups: (i) Engineering Students, University of Kalyani, Nadia, W.B (N=30) (ii) Social Studies Students, University of Kalyani, Nadia, W.B (N=30).

The psychological status Stress of adult university students were measured through Questionnaire of A.K.Srivastava (2001).

To find out the significance differences in psychological status between the groups, Analysis of ‘t’ test was conducted. The significance of means were tested at $p < 0.05$ level in this study. For the calculations, the excel spread sheet of window version 7 was used.

Interpretation of the score: for the present study researcher has to use questionnaire tool for data collection. There were 50 questions and maximum score was 200 and minimum score was 00 respectively. In this study Five point Likert Scale is used for data collection. The responses, indicating degree of strength of attitude are 1) Always, 2) Often, 3) Frequently, 4) Sometime, 5) Never.

Data interpretation: The Stress Levels are as follow based on the A.K.Srivastava (2001).

Stress				
	Stress Coping	Low Deficient	Moderate	High Deficient
Active Coping	Behavioral Approach	0-29	30-45	46-60
	Cognitive Approach	0-11	12-18	19-24
	Cognitive-Behavioral Approach	0-15	16-24	25-32
Avoiding Coping	Behavioral Avoidance	0-27	28-42	43-56
	Cognitive Avoidance	0-13	14-21	22-26

2.1. Criterion Measures

The researcher measured the Personal Data and Psychological Variables of the subjects. The measured Personal Data and Psychological Components were as follows-

Table-1: The Personal Data and Psychological Variables measurements

Variables		Measuring Unit	Measured by/ through	
Personal data	Age	Years	DOB	
	Height	Cm	Measuring tape	
	Weight	Kg	Weighing machine	
Psychological variables	Stress	Behavioral Approach	Score	Questionnaire
		Cognitive Approach		
		Cognitive-Behavioral Approach		
		Behavioral Avoidance		
		Cognitive Avoidance		

3. Result

The result of the study of selected Psychological Variables and their statistical analysis has been presented in the following heads-

3.1. Psychological Variables Stress (Active coping) between the two groups were presented below-

Table No. 2. Descriptive statistics of Stress (Active coping) between Engineering and Social Science Students

Group	N	Behavioral Approach	Cognitive Approach	Cognitive Behavioral Approach
		Mean±SD	Mean±SD	Mean±SD
Engineering Student	30	30.97±6.42	11.87±2.86	16.93±3.93
Social Science Student	30	24.23±7.49	11.77±3.39	13.0±4.14

Table no-2 indicate that the mean and SD value in respect of Behavioral Approach, Cognitive Approach and Cognitive Behavioral Approach of the Engineering Student and Social Science Student were 30.97 ± 6.42 , 11.87 ± 2.86 , 16.93 ± 3.93 and 24.23 ± 7.49 , 11.77 ± 3.39 , 13.0 ± 4.14 respectively.

Fig-1: Psychological Variables Stress (Active coping) between the two groups were presented below-

3.1. Comparative statistics of Psychological Variables Stress (Active coping) between the two groups were presented below-

Table No. 3. Testing significance of mean difference of two groups of Psychological Variables Stress (Active Coping) were presented below-

Variavles	Group	Mean Difference	SED	DF	t-Ratio
Behavioral Approach	Engineering Student	6.7	1.80	58	3.74*s
	Social Science Student				
Cognitive Approach	Engineering Student	0.1	0.81		
	Social Science Student				
Cognitive Behavioral Approach	Engineering Student	3.93	1.04		3.77*s
	Social Science Student				

*The table values required for significance at $t_{0.05}$ level with DF (58) was 1.67

Form the table no-3, the researcher observes that Behavioral Approach between Engineering Student and Social Science Student. The mean difference of were computed and the t value was found 3.74* which is statically significant difference

at 0.05 level of significance. According the A.K.Srivastava (2001) Stress Norms (behavioral approach), the Engineering Student possess **moderate** deficient Stress Level, whereas Social Science Students possess **low** deficient Stress Level.

While the researcher observes that Cognitive Approach between Engineering Student and Social Science Student. The mean difference of were computed and the t value was found 0.12. Through some difference was observed between the mean values but no significant differences were exists. According the A.K.Srivastava (2001) Stress Norms (Cognitive Approach), the both Engineering Student and Social Science Students possess **moderate** deficient Stress Level.

The researcher also observes that Cognitive Behavioral Approach between Engineering Student and Social Science Student. The mean difference of were computed and the t value was found 3.77* which is statically significant difference at 0.05 level of significance. According the A.K.Srivastava (2001) Stress Norms (Cognitive Behavioral Approach), the Engineering Student possess **moderate** deficient Stress Level, whereas Social Science Students possess **low** deficient Stress Level.

3.2. Psychological Variables Stress (Avoiding Coping) between the two groups were presented below-

Table No. 4. Descriptive statistics of stress (Avoiding Coping) between Engineering and Social Science Students

Group	N	Behavioral Avoidance	Cognitive Voidance
		Mean±SD	Mean±SD
Engineering Student	30	21.73±5.99	14.30±4.64
Social Science Student	30	15.43±6.11	10.77±4.07

Table no-4 indicate that the mean and SD value in respect of Behavioral Avoidance, Cognitive Avoidance of the Engineering Student and Social Science Student were 21.73±5.99, 15.43±6.11 and 14.30±4.64, 10.77±4.07 respectively.

Fig-2: Psychological Variables Stress (Avoiding Coping) between the two groups were presented below-

3.1. Comparative statistics of Psychological Variables Stress (Avoiding Coping) between the two groups were presented below-

Table No. 5. Testing significance of mean difference of two groups of Psychological Variables Stress (Avoiding Coping) were presented below-

Variavles	Group	Mean Difference	SED	DF	t-Ratio
Behavioral Avoidance	Engineering Student	6.3	1.56	58	4.03*s
	Social Science Student				
Cognitive Avoidance	Engineering Student	3.53	1.23		3.13*s
	Social Science Student				

*The table values required for significance at $t_{0.05}$ level with DF (58) was 1.67

Form the table no-5, the researcher observes that Behavioral Avoidance between Engineering Student and Social Science Student. The mean difference of were computed and the t value was found 4.03* which is statically significant difference at 0.05 level of significance. According the A.K.Srivastava (2001) Stress Norms (Behavioral Avoidance), the both Engineering Student and Social Science Students possess **low** deficient Stress Level.

The researcher also observes that Cognitive Avoidance between Engineering Student and Social Science Student. The mean difference of were computed and the t value was found 3.13* which is statically significant difference at 0.05 level of significance. According the A.K.Srivastava (2001) Stress Norms (Cognitive Avoidance), the Engineering Student possess **moderate** deficient Stress Level, whereas Social Science Students possess **low** deficient Stress Level.

4. Discussion

The purpose of the study is to survey the psychological status of Kalyani University students who are Engineering Students and Social Science Students. Psychological variable Stress was measured through the Questionnaire of A.K.Srivastava (2001). After the analysis of data it was observed that the Engineering Students were experiencing **Moderate Stress Level** in Behavioral Approach, Cognitive Approach and Cognitive Behavioral Approach (30.97 ± 6.42 , 11.87 ± 2.86 and 16.93 ± 3.93 respectively) whereas the Social Studies Students were experiencing **Low Stress Level** in Behavioral Approach and Cognitive Behavioral Approach (24.23 ± 7.49 and 13.0 ± 4.14 respectively) and **Moderate Level** possess only in Cognitive Approach (11.77 ± 3.39). The finding shows that the Engineering Students possess better ability of understanding design and its implementation, can observe barriers and facilities. Both the groups were found experiencing **Moderate Stress level** in Cognitive Approach which shows that both the groups are better in mental abilities which include thinking, remembering, learning and using languages.

Engineering Students were also found experiencing **Moderate Stress level** and the social studies students were found **Low Stress Level** in Cognitive Behavioral Approach and Cognitive Avoidance (16.93 ± 3.93 and 14.30 ± 4.64 respectively), which shows that Engineering Students possess more ability of dealing the situation of maintenance of addictive behaviors. As well as the Engineering Students were found better dealing with the situation which initiate in anxious thought and feeling.

Both the groups were found experiencing **Low Stress Level** in Behavioral Avoidance (21.73 ± 5.99 and 15.43 ± 6.11) which shows that Engineering as well as Social Studies Students tries to escape or distract themselves from difficult thoughts, feeling and situations.

4. Conclusions

The study throws up the following findings:-

- Engineering students were found experiencing moderate stress level in behavioral approach, cognitive approach, cognitive behavioral approach, cognitive avoidance and low stress level possess only in behavioral avoidance which can be the rigorous curriculum that trigger stress, irritation, nervousness or management problem.
- Social studies student were found experiencing low stress level in behavioral approach, cognitive behavioral approach, cognitive avoidance, behavioral avoidance and moderate stress level possess only in cognitive approach.

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